

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Dstl – Anthrax and nerve agent detector

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Identification of hazardous
chemical and biological
contamination on surfaces
using spectral signatures

Data Study Group Final Report: Dstl – Anthrax and nerve agent detector

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1 Introduction

The assessment of surfaces for potential contamination by biological hazards (e.g. the causative agent of anthrax, *Bacillus anthracis*) and chemical hazards (e.g. nerve agents such as VX) is relevant for a range of defence and biosecurity applications. To this end, the Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (Dstl) and through a competition run by the Defence and Security Accelerator (DASA) have provided a dataset collected using a range of different sensor modalities that have measured various surfaces contaminated with surrogate bacteria, hazardous chemicals and relevant control materials. The identification of the contaminate from the underlying surface material poses a significant challenge not easily solved using conventional techniques.

The current methods to detect, locate and report hazardous biological and chemical materials incur operative, logistic and temporal burdens when various factors are taken into consideration, which may include sampling, removal of the sample to laboratory infrastructure, sample processing and analysis. Additionally, many biodetection systems are large and require mains power, regular maintenance and a constant supply of consumables (for example, reagents) to operate. These systems are typically complex to use and are only operable by skilled end users. The practical use of which, in the field, render such technologies both cost and time inefficient and impractical for rapid analysis.

In order to address these issues, Dstl and DASA conducted research into prototype systems with industrial and academic partners. These efforts have focused on the development of innovative sensor technologies that could ultimately lead to fieldable systems, to provide rapid, high-confidence detection, location and identification of biological and chemical hazards deposited over a wide area. Successful detection technologies require the consideration, and ultimately the optimisation, of a range of parameters. These include speed of response and low false alarm rate in a range of environments (for example the system does not alarm to natural and anthropogenic background microbiomes). The complication of the detection scheme being employed on a dynamic range of field conditions pose the technical challenge of integrating the sensor detection scheme and accurate analysis into a fieldable unit.

1.1 Challenge overview

Hazardous chemical and biological materials pose an invisible threat and are technically challenging to detect, but doing so has the potential to save lives. Molecular spectroscopy techniques [1] provide information rich chemical signatures which have been shown in the literature to discriminate between different bacterial species and chemical hazards.

From a biological and chemical sensing perspective, Dstl has coordinated a combined research effort (funded by UK Ministry of Defence) in a competition run by DASA, where Dstl produced a standardised set of sample surfaces contaminated with simulants for chemical and biological hazards. This sample set was sent to seven institutions, with underpinning research at Dstl, who have

developed and applied different spectroscopic technologies to the samples to generate a range of spectral based data. Likewise spectral signatures of a range of deposited chemical agents have been collected through research at Dstl, as part of a technology demonstrator programme. This sample set comprises of three different surfaces, with four deposited agents across two spectroscopic techniques. This will generate a unique multi-technology dataset from a standardised sample set and as far as we know this is the first time this has been attempted. The challenge is the combined analysis of the large dataset obtained from these multiple technologies to successfully identify biological and chemical hazards.

This report presents the outputs of a week-long Data Study Group hosted by the Alan Turing Institute on a challenge presented by Dstl during 9th – 13th December 2019. The scope was to investigate how data science and machine learning techniques can be applied to recognise and discriminate between biological and chemical of sample surfaces contaminated with simulants for chemical and biological hazards on different surfaces analysed using a range of spectroscopic sensors and techniques.

The aim of the project is to address the application of machine learning to identify surface deposited bacterial species and chemical hazards from their spectral signatures, including situations where significant spectral contributions are generated from the background surface.

1.2 Data overview

The sample sets produced at Dstl comprised of four different substrate surfaces including plastic, metal, glass and wood. Each substrate contained a colour coded dot in the upper left corner (used for identification of the agent) and three \times 5 microlitre sample deposits of varying concentrations (100%, 10%, 1% dilutions respectively).

The biological data set consisted of spores of two bacterial species that are common simulants for Bacillus anthracis (causative agent of anthrax, see Table 1) and the third being Polystyrene Latex Microspheres (PSL). PSL was used in place of bacteria as a challenging control, as polystyrene has a rich spectral complexity in terms of spectral peak response, and due to its size is of approximately 1 micrometer, which is in the same order of magnitude as the bacterial spores. PSL was selected to confirm that the information being produced was biochemical in nature (.i.e. related to the vibrational energies of their molecular bonds) and specific to the spores and not related to their physical characteristics .e.g. size and shape.

The chemical sample set was also constructed to the same specification as the biological set. It however, consisted of four types of chemical deposits, two of which containing hazardous chemicals Mustard gas (T) and V-Series, which is a nerve agent (VX variant). The third, dibenzoxazepine (CR) is a riot control agent (RCA) and the fourth is triethyl phosphate (TEPO), which is used as a “stimulant”, which is defined as a chemical that has a similar enough physical properties to chemical agents that it can be used as a less hazardous substitute

Substrate	Chemical	Substrate	Biological
Plastic	T	Plastic	BG
Glass	VX	Glass	BT
Metal	CR	Metal	PSL
Sand	TEPO	Wood	

Table 1: List of sample substrates used and hazardous deposits/simulants. These include three chemical agents Mustard gas (T), dibenzoxazepine (CR), triethyl phosphate (TEPO) and a nerve agent V-Series (VX variant). Biological deposits include two similar bacteria closely related to the anthrax pathogen; *Bacillus atrophaeus* (BG), *Bacillus thuringiensis* (BT) and Polystyrene Latex Microspheres (PSL) used in place of bacteria. Permutations of all substrates vs chemical or biological agents were create and sent to the institute labs.

during experiments.

In a separate effort, spectral signatures of a range of deposited chemical hazards have been collected on prototype systems at Dstl. The details of the sample substrate and the chemical/biological deposits are shown in Table 1. The sample set comprises four different surfaces, with three deposited hazards across two spectroscopic techniques. This generated a unique multi-technology dataset from the standardized sample set.

Eight different institutions were provided with the samples created at Dstl. Two institutions analysed the chemical samples and six were given the anthrax related bacteria. A number of spectroscopic analysis techniques were employed at the institutions including fluorescence, microwave and multiple types of infrared. Two institutes used image scanning techniques that scanned the 2D sample surface to produce a spectrum at each point (pixel), generating a 3-dimensional (hyperspectral) dataset rather than a single spectrum for the entire sample target. The details of each dataset generated at each institution is shown in Table 2.

1.3 Main objectives

The main aim of the data study group was exploration of data generated from the institutions using different spectroscopic techniques in order to investigate the following:

1. Determination of the feasibility of automated classification through unsupervised approaches where no groundtruth is available.
2. Evaluation of automated supervised approaches to differentiate biological and/or chemical agents in the 1D spectroscopic data, where groundtruth labeled data is available.
3. Extension to the 3D data through identification of suitable automated strategies for delineating hazard and background locations in the unlabelled 3D data.

Hazard type	Institute	Dataset Size	Method	Dimensions (Rank)
Chemical	2	58	IR absorption	1×119 (1)
Chemical	3	62	IR absorption	1×62 (1)
Biological	4	120	Microwave	$(1 + 1i) \times 20001$ (1)
Biological	5	44	Fluorescence	$88 \times 324 \times 78$ (3)
Biological	6	85	IR-QCL	$21 \times 21 \times 112$ (3)
Biological	7	402	2D-IR	Various $(404 - 502) \times 257 \times \tau$ (time) (2)
Biological	8	526	FTIR	1×1672 (1)
Biological	9	131	ATR-FTIR	1×1762 or 1×1668 (1)

Table 2: Data characteristics from different institutions including technologies employed; Infrared absorption (IR), Microwave, 2D Infrared (2D-IR), Fluorescence, IR absorption - quantum cascade laser (IR-QCL), Fourier transformed infrared reflectance (FTIR), Fourier transformed infrared attenuated total reflectance (ATR-FTIR)

4. Evaluation of performance improvements achievable by exploiting the increased dataset size of the 3D data.

1.4 Approach

- We first explored the relationship between the signal response and the concentration of the substance under investigation. This would inform whether parametric statistical modelling could be used, or more data-driven non-linear machine learning methods would be more appropriate.
- Based on this we explored a number of linear and non-linear multiclass classification techniques including logistic regression, support vector machine (SVM) and convolution neural networks (CNN) on single dimensional datasets. As labels, we explored differentiating hazardous substances, but generalising the various substrates to a single class.
- The 3D data gave us the opportunity to increase the training dataset substantially. On this data, we were able to prototype various deep learning techniques in more detail, including multiclass embedding.

1.5 Main conclusions

1. The application of dimensionality reduction techniques such as principal component analysis when applied to infrared spectra reveal structure within the data and provide sufficient information within the first three principal components such that classifiers can be accurately trained within

this reduced feature space. In particular, random forests and K-nearest neighbours were most successful.

2. 3D (hyperspectral) datasets, in comparison to single point spectral measurements, can provide an increase in the labelled data set size when a semi-automated segmentation approach is applied.
3. Deep learning shows potential on infrared spectroscopic data, which could be expanded implementation of surface scanning techniques, to generate 3D spectral data sets.

1.6 Limitations

1. In the labelled infrared spectra, it was noted that during the drying process the biological simulants formed 'coffee rings', therefore spectra labelled as bacteria may contain concentrations of biological material, below the detection limit of the system.
2. The number of measured labelled infrared spectra also exhibit uneven distribution of samples taken for biological versus non-biological (e.g. controls and surfaces) samples.
3. The 3D fluorescence spectra was provided unlabelled, with datasets both preprocessed and unprocessed. Details of the preprocessing methods were not available to the study participants to protect proprietary IP. These factors increased the complexity of the task.

Due to the nature of the project all the data was classified as "Tier 2" which resulted in restricted access. This entailed that all analysis was conducted on the state-of-the-art Turing Safe Haven platform. The platform is a secure cloud environment designed for the analysis of sensitive datasets. Unfortunately during the week challenges were encountered using this system including latency on the virtual machine (VM) and insufficient resources needed for training deep learning classifiers and for enabling the team to work efficiently simultaneously. Connection stability and data bandwidth of the wireless network was also intermittent, resulting in the team being split across different locations in order to access the VM. These factors hindered progress and achievement in the limited time frame.

1.7 Recommendations and further work

While the results are encouraging, the limitations revealed during the data study week indicate that more input data is needed, particularly of bare substrate, for higher accuracy across multiple backgrounds. However, this can be mitigated by utilising data rich 3D scanning spectral techniques to increase the number of background samples. In addition, a larger representation of backgrounds that would be expected in real situations would give greater clarification of transferability of these techniques. Training methods that are tested here on higher

dimensional data containing pairs of background and using multiple sources are another way to potentially increase the transferability of these results to unseen samples.

2 Quantitative problem formulation

Optical spectroscopy measures the absorption and emission of photons on a given sample over a range of wavelengths; the recorded signal is related both to the characteristics of the material and the density/concentration of the material being studied. If this response was linear one might expect to be able to model the problem as a mixture model with foreground (hazardous material) and background (substrate) components and directly infer the probability of presence and concentration of the hazardous material. However, in reality the response is potentially non-linear with significant interaction effects between the foreground and background. Moreover, unwanted artefacts like specular reflection and inconsistent illumination/scaling are important factors.

Given the potential non-linear presentation of the data and TDSG time restrictions, it was deemed infeasible to model a mixture proportion between hazard and substrate. Instead, a multiclass classification approach was proposed that would distinguish between hazard type and no hazard. Substrate type could have a massive effect on the data, hence it is interesting also to look at whether specific classes for substrate type could be learned for improved accuracy but loss of generality (to new substrate types).

There are similarities between individual spectroscopic signatures and one dimensional time series data such as autocorrelation. This led to the idea that methods showing success in classifying time series data may have similar results for spectroscopic data. One of these methods is residual neural networks. These are convolutional neural networks with residual links that reduce the information loss commonly found in deep neural nets. The advantages in using convolutional neural networks are the identification of features through the application of filters, and that with the inclusion of a global average pooling rather than fully connected layer it is possible to view which areas of the spectra are being used in the classification decision through class activation maps.

In order to apply machine learning techniques to the 3-dimensional fluorescence dataset effectively, an automated delineation technique had to be developed. The algorithm had to accurately and efficiently identify irregular shapes containing data of interest, that is to classify regions of the biological agent being measured and identify the substrate background. The spatial information in relation to the chemical/biological agent and the background needed to be assimilated. Using this information a sample labelling mask (which in essence is equivalent to a bit mask where the region of interest is represented by a “1” and the background by a “0” respectively) for the machine learning algorithm can then be created and deployed.

3 Data overview

Each of the eight institutions received a combination of prepared samples, each containing 3 deposits of varying concentrations (100%, 10%, 1% dilutions) of either a chemical or biological sample (T mustard, VX, CR, PSL, TEPO, BT, BG) on five different types of substrates including wood, glass, plastic, sand and metal (see Table 1 for more details). The resulting datasets generated by each institution varied greatly in both complexity and dimensionality due to the different techniques they employed. A summary of each dataset, including their size, complexity and rank (dimensions) can be seen in Table 2.

3.1 Dataset description

Due to the restricted time frame and resources, full exploratory data analysis of the full datasets from all eight institutions was deemed impractical. We identified three datasets that would most likely yield achievable results in the restricted time frame. We considered datasets from the institutions that would provide a larger number of data points when compared to others using similar spectral methods. The first set of data are both 1-dimensional in nature with a reasonable number of data-points per sample. The first is from institution 2, which contained chemical samples in 58 data files each consisting of a 1D array of 119 points. The second is from institution eight containing biological samples over 526 data files, each a 1D array of 1672 sample points. The third dataset chosen was from institution 5, which consisted of 44 biological datasets each containing a 3D data cube with $88 \times 324 \times 78$ sample points over four different substrates.

3.2 Data overview and exploratory analysis

In the preliminary data exploration of the 3-dimensional dataset from institution 5 we noted unbalanced data for some classes (.e.g. wood). The nature of the data meant that labels needed to be annotated to delineate the biological compound from the background substrate. Due to the complexity of this dataset manually labelling was not feasible, therefore we needed to develop a signal processing algorithm that would automatically identify both biological compound and different substrates.

After the preliminary analysis of the data and within the limited time frame available, we decided to develop two different approaches to tackle single point (1D) spectral measurements and scanning (3D) spectral measurements. The aim would be to tailor algorithms and techniques to maximise the amount of useful results within the short time period. In this section we did a preliminary exploration of the datasets with the intent on formulating the best approach to analyse the data and identify which machine learning techniques would be most applicable.

Figure 1: Bacterial deposits on glass dataset. Raw unprocessed data plotted in all plots. Top row: Animation showing the spatial location (x,y axis) and concentration (intensity) for 280 nm illumination, and scanning the different frequencies along the z-axis from 400 nm to 700 nm. Bottom row depicts the same for 365 nm illumination.

3.2.1 Visualisation by slicing a data cube

The three dimensional datasets (a data cube) provided by institution 5 had the following dimensions: $88 \times 324 \times 78$ (x, y, z). The x and y coordinates represented the spatial coordinates of the sample in relation to the 2D surface. Each slice along the z dimension represents the resulting image detected at the detector at a specific wavelength starting from 400 nm and ascending to 700 nm at 78 different incremental steps. Each sample contained two data cubes containing the results from two illumination sources, the first at 280 nm and the second at 365 nm. We began by creating a visualisation tool that would allow us to quickly view this complex data by generating an animation of the 2D sample surface, while scanning through 78 wavelengths that were detected at the detector. The tool was able to plot both data cubes simultaneously and also plot a cross-section of the data cube along the most interesting features of the 2D surface.

Figure 2: Bacterial deposits on glass dataset with Anscombe transformation (see section 8.1). Top row: Animation showing the spatial location (x,y axis) and concentration (intensity) for the 280 nm illumination, and scanning the different frequencies along the z-axis from 400 nm to 700 nm. Bottom row depicts the same for 365 nm illumination.

Note: *The Figures 1-5 are generated using an Animation feature in **PDFs** which has allowed us to embed the animated output of the visualisation tool in this document. In order to fully appreciate and play-back the animation in this document, you will need to open this **PDF** on **Windows 10** with **Adobe Acrobat Reader**.*

Figure 1 is an exploratory animation of a bacterial samples deposited on glass substrate, this data set has been preprocessed by the institution in order to remove ambient light sources and reflections. As you can see, the three deposits are barely visible on the 280 nm source. The two higher concentrations of the bacterial deposit can be seen on the 365 nm source. We then applied an Anscombe transform [2] to this dataset (see Figure 2), which is a variance-stabilising transformation that transforms Poisson distributed noise into an approximate Gaussian distribution (see section 8.1 for more details). More of the features of the biological deposited samples can be seen. We then looked at the raw dataset, Figure 3 (before any preprocessing) for the same sample, here multiple ambient light sources and reflections are received at the detector. Also note the typical coffee cup stain like pattern of the least concentrated biological

Figure 3: Bacterial deposits on raw glass dataset. Top row: Animation showing the spatial location (x,y axis) and concentration (intensity) for the 280 nm illumination, and scanning the different frequencies along the z-axis from 400 nm to 700 nm. Bottom row depicts the same for 365 nm illumination.

sample. This illustrates the inhomogeneous drying patterns for these samples deposited on to surfaces. In order to illustrate the effect of different substrate materials, Figure 4 shows an animation of the Wood substrate; here you can clearly see the effect of material on the visibility of the deposited samples and the need to produce an automated technique that will identify irregular regions against a background signal. Figure 5 is again the wood sample, but illustrates how ambient light sources and reflections can severely hide the information of interest and demonstrates the importance of developing effective preprocessing steps.

3.2.2 Principal component analysis (PCA)

An initial PCA was performed on data from institution 8 after reducing the wavenumber range to the fingerprint region between $600\text{-}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$, as shown in Figure 6a. The first two principal components are shown to contain the majority of the information, as seen in the scree plot in Figure 6b. The visualisation of the space and the PCA of the top 2 and 3 principal components are shown in Figures 6c and 6d. These figures aid visualisation of the distribution and

Figure 4: Bacterial deposits on wood dataset. Top row: Animation showing the spatial location (x,y axis) and concentration (intensity) for the 280 nm illumination, and scanning the different frequencies along the z-axis from 400 nm to 700 nm. Bottom row depicts the same for 365 nm illumination.

separability of the data in up to three dimensions, and provides a preliminary indication of how well a classification algorithm might perform on the data.

We used combined institute 2 (chemical IR) and 8 (biological IR) spectral data for performing dimensionality reduction using PCA. Each spectrum was truncated on the wavenumber 1000-1500 cm^{-1} and interpolated on the domain (1000, 1005, 1010, ..., 1495). Then, a sum normalisation on the intensities was performed (so that the sum of intensities equalled one). This reduced the original dimension from 1667 (in the case of institute 8 data) to 100. Any sample with insufficient data over the wavenumber region 1000-1500 cm^{-1} was dropped. A PCA could then be performed using 578 of the labelled samples from institutes 2 and 8. In Figures 7a - 9f we plot some exploratory data analysis on both institution 2 and 8 in the subspace of the top 3 principal components (which explains 97% of the variation).

Figure 8 plots all the samples, labelled by deposit material. We can see ‘spokes’ of data for the different deposit materials emanating from the origin (predominantly for BG, BT and PSL), which gives us a clear hint that the spectra do indeed occupy different regions in this reduced dimension subspace.

We also plot ‘slices’ of the data, firstly split by substrate material in Figures

Figure 5: Bacterial deposits on raw wood dataset. Top row: Animation showing the spatial location (x,y axis) and concentration (intensity) for the 280 nm illumination, and scanning the different frequencies along the z-axis from 400 nm to 700 nm. Bottom row depicts the same for 365 nm illumination.

10-15, and labelled by deposit material. Note that in the dataset, not every agent was tested on each substrate, and some substrate materials have relatively few samples, such as wood and sand. Regardless, these plots do illustrate that there is still separability in the data once the substrate material has been controlled for. It also seems that the glass substrate is the main contributor to the variability in the data, as the long spokes along principal axes 1 from Figure 7 also appear in Figure 7d. This is again apparent from Figure 8, which plots all the samples labelled by substrate material.

In Figures 9a-9f, we plot slices of the data split by deposit material, and labelled by substrate material. From Figures 9d-9f, it is evident that the samples for the chemical agents occupy only a small region of the subspace, compared to the biological and non-hazardous samples.

(a) Fingerprint region of 600-1800 cm^{-1} used in PCA analysis.

(b) Scree plot of PCA explained variance.

(c) 2D PCA plot of the first two principal components of institution 8.

(d) 3D PCA plot of the first three principal components of institution 8.

Figure 6: PCA analysis of institute 8.

(a) All substrate materials.

(b) Plastic substrate material.

(c) Metal substrate material.

(d) Glass substrate material.

(e) Sand substrate material.

(f) Wood substrate material.

Figure 7: PCA for substrate materials, labelled by deposit material. Some substrate materials (particularly plastic, metal and glass) are more represented in the data.

Figure 8: All deposit materials, labelled by substrate material. The glass samples appear to contribute to most of the variation along the first principal axis.

4 Experiment: Logistic regression classifiers on reduced dimension subspaces

As an initial step, multiclass classification on the first 3 principal components was carried out on the institution 8 data.

This was used as a way to assess the relative utility of an approach to train a classifier on a reduced dimension subspace.

4.1 Data and experimental set-up

The data analysed is the institution 8 PCA transformed data. The data is made up of the first 3 principal components from the PCA. There are four possible classifier outputs in the data: bare substrates (BareSubs), polystyrene (PSL), BG and BT.

The data from institution 8 was made up of 526 labelled IR spectra. One data instance was removed as the data was a different length than the other samples. From the useable 525 experiments, a 75-25 train-test split was generated resulting in a training sample of size 394 and a testing sample of size 131 (see Table 3). Splitting a dataset into training and testing groups allows the model to learn the discriminating features present in the data whilst retaining the ability to assess the model performance on data not used to train the model [7]. This approach prevents data leakage.

(a) Non-hazardous deposit materials.

(b) BG deposit material.

(c) BT deposit material.

(d) CR deposit material.

(e) T deposit material.

(f) VX deposit material.

Figure 9: PCA for deposit materials, labelled by substrate material. The data was imbalanced more towards biological and non-hazardous samples, while the chemical samples appear to occupy a small region of the subspace.

Output Name	Output Code	Comments	Train Split	Test Split
BareSubs	1	Used for calibration	12	4
BG	2	Biological Compound	183	61
BT	3	Biological Compound	114	38
PSL	4	Polystyrene	85	28

Table 3: Summary of the data for the different substrates and the corresponding machine learning training and test split per substrate.

	1	2	3	4
1	0	4	0	0
2	0	44	0	17
3	0	17	11	10
4	0	9	0	19

Table 4: Confusion matrix, where the rows are the true class and the columns represent the predicted class.

4.2 Method and results

The analysis was conducted in R using the packages dplyr, nnet, caret and caTools. The classification method used on this problem is multinomial logistic regression. This approach was used as it is a standard baseline in multiclass classification problems [8]. Due to the strict time constraints, the priority in modelling was to focus on the standard approach with the least computational time required.

The following Table 4 is the confusion matrix for the four-class problem. The multinomial logistic regression gave a train and test accuracy of 0.63 and 0.56 respectively.

4.3 Discussion

There is a small difference between the train and test accuracies, with the train accuracy higher than that of test. This could suggest that there may be some overfitting. The model does not seem to perform classification very well, partly due to the imbalanced classes present in the data. The model could not classify correctly the bare substrate due to its small incidence in the data. To improve the model’s ability to discriminate between the samples, a greater sample size is required, specifically the bare substrate. In addition, in the analysis, three class-classification was attempted, classifying between biological compounds (both BG and BT), bare substrate and polystyrene. Despite producing higher accuracy figures, these results were deemed irrelevant as the number of the samples in each class were significantly disproportionate with one another, thus incontrovertibly biasing the accuracy score to favour the class with the most samples. This resulted in four-class being chosen as it can classify better between the groups, offering more insight, despite having a lower accuracy.

5 Experiment: Further classifiers on reduced dimension subspaces

The analysis in Section 3.2.2 and experiment in Section 4 so far investigate the extent to which:

- Dimension reduction via PCA preserves the variability of spectra data.
- How successful logistic regression is at forming separating regions in the reduced dimension subspaces.

In this section, we aim to extend our analysis in Section 4 by considering institution 2 data (in addition to institution 8) and applying various classification algorithms (other than logistic regression).

5.1 Experimental set-up

Using the processed IR data from institutions 2 and 8, we trained several multilabel classifiers. In these classifiers we had three types of data inputs (based on the first three principle components from the PCA) and 6 output categories based on the classes 0, BG, BT, CR, T and VX. Where, class '0' denotes 'non-hazardous' materials including polystyrene (PSL), bare substrate and BG and BT are bacterial agents, while CR, TEPO, T and VX are chemical agents.

From a labelled dataset of 578 IR spectra from institutions 2 and 8, a 75-25 train-test split was generated to give a train set size of 433 and a test set size of 145.

5.2 Methods

The classifiers were trained in Scikit-learn. Due to the limited compute resources available within the secure cloud environment, coupled with the strict time constraint, minimal hyperparameter tuning was performed on each of the learning algorithms (.i.e. most were run with their default settings).

For classifiers which are not traditionally multiclass (e.g. SVMs, Gaussian processes), we use the "one-vs-rest" functionality in scikit-learn to extend them to multiclass classification.

5.3 Results: Test/train accuracy

Here the total number spectra is divided into two separate sets of data, the first being the "*training set*" and the second the "*test set*". The "*training set*" of spectra is first inserted into the machine learning algorithm and a classifier is produced. The resulting classifier is then employed to classify any new spectra. In order to test how well the classifier will perform, we then use the "*test set*" of data and feed it into the classifier and assess its performance as the classification of these spectra are already known. Effectively we are trying to simulate what

we could expect how well the classifier will perform with new spectra that is not present in the original dataset.

Table 5 displays the train/test accuracy results for each of the 6-way multiclass classifiers. We re-emphasise that in these experiments, test set classification performance is not the main goal; rather the objective is to compare different classification algorithms in forming separating regions. We observe that the train and test accuracy is quite similar for most of the algorithms (and in some cases, the test accuracy is above the train accuracy). We suggested some reasons for this.

- Low dimension feature space – as the PCA transform maps to three dimensions, this results in high sample to feature ratio of 578:3. This makes it ‘easier’ for an algorithm to generalise, thus we anticipate train and test performance to be quite close.
- There may be some minor data leakage, as due to time constraints, the same PCA transformation that was used in exploratory data analysis in Section 3.4.2 was applied before conducting the train-test split. Since this applies to all the classifiers trained however, it largely does not affect comparative performance.

As for comparisons between algorithms, the test accuracies for KNN and random forests are the highest, and on-par with each other. We attained 100% training accuracy using random forests, but we believe that this was due to overfitting, since the test accuracy was 80% (we reiterate that all classifiers were trained with minimal hyperparameter tuning).

Classifier	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy
Multinomial logistic regression	0.44	0.44
Linear support vector machine (SVM)	0.47	0.52
K-nearest neighbours (KNN)	0.84	0.77
Quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA)	0.63	0.63
Random forest	1.00	0.80
Gaussian process	0.48	0.52
Shallow neural network (1 hidden layer)	0.61	0.63
Deep neural network (3 hidden layer)	0.67	0.70

Table 5: Results of the six-way multiclass classifier.

The confusion matrix for Random forest on test set (size 145) is shown in 6.

5.4 Visualisation of classification region

Figures 10a - 10f depict the classification regions of the trained classifiers. Non-linear or nonparametric classifiers such as random forests, QDA, KNN or NNs appear to be better at separating classes with non-linear boundaries. However, we might hypothesise that most of the space should be categorised as non-hazardous, and only small sub-regions should be hazardous materials. This is

(a) Linear SVM

(b) KNN

(c) QDA

(d) Random Forest

(e) Shallow Neural Network

(f) Deep Neural Network

Figure 10: Classification regions for the trained classifiers, showing how the different classifiers form their separating regions.

	0	1-BG	2-BT	3-CR	4-T	5-VX
0	26	3	4	0	0	1
1-BG	2	53	4	0	0	0
2-BT	2	8	34	0	0	0
3-CR	0	1	0	1	0	0
4-T	1	1	0	0	1	1
5-VX	0	0	0	0	1	1

Table 6: The rows display the true class. The columns show the predicted class.

purely based on the intuition that the majority of everyday materials would be deemed non-hazardous. Thus it is not immediately clear how these trained classifiers would generalise to application in the field.

5.5 Discussion

The random forest had the best train and test accuracy. Notably, there are 5 examples which were actually hazardous that were classified as not hazardous, which represents a false negative rate of 4.5%. Arguably, a false negative (classifying something as non-hazardous when it is hazardous) may be treated as being more dangerous than a false positive (classifying something as hazardous when it is non-hazardous). Hence keeping the false negative rate small is ideal. For the five false negatives, the random forest predicted class probabilities are shown in Table 5. A plot of a misclassified false negative in Figure 11, this point is more challenging to classify correctly due to the low margin between it and other classes in the projection, on the reduced dimensions of the PC subspace.

	0	1-BG	2-BT	3-CR	4-T	5-VX
Example 1	0.88	0.12	0	0	0	0
Example 2	0.74	0.18	0.08	0	0	0
Example 3	0.42	0.21	0.37	0	0	0
Example 4	0.61	0.14	0.25	0	0	0
Example 5	0.54	0.15	0.27	0	0.03	0.01

Table 7: Results of the 5 false negatives for the random forest predicted class probabilities. The actual class probability highlighted in bold.

We did not explicitly investigate how other confounding factors, such as substrate material, might affect classification performance. This might be a direction for future work. As a counterpoint however, the substrate material may not be known in field applications, so classification without including the substrate material as a feature would be of great benefit.

We used up to three dimensions for PCA, because it makes it easy to visualise both the PCA transformed data and resulting classification regions. Further work would investigate whether higher dimensional PCA could yield better

Figure 11: Misclassification of a false negative (T falsely misclassified as non-hazardous), because it is very close to other non-hazardous points.

classification performance, with the tradeoff being a requirement for more samples.

When comparing different classification algorithms, we found that classical methods like KNN and random forests performed well ‘out of the box’. But it is possible that more modern methods such as deep neural networks might perform as well or better, given appropriate hyperparameter tuning and a larger dataset to train on.

Our analysis uncovers some key takeaways about the distribution of training data and class imbalance. Ultimately, the PCA transformation will be affected by the distribution of samples. Many of the samples used were for biological agents, and moreover much of the variation in the samples was due to the glass substrate material. The performance of the classification algorithms hinge on the test distribution being representative of the training distribution. Therefore, when designing experiments for collecting additional data, it is important to consider the distribution of samples that might be encountered in field operation.

6 Experiment: Unsupervised clustering

In this experiment we investigated unsupervised clustering approaches to discriminate contaminants in order to understand more about the problem.

6.1 Data utility measure: Statistical tests to choose the best predictive model

For choosing a suitable predictive methodology, it is useful to understand the relationship among the features/predictors (in this case intensity and wave length). To this end, correlation between two features are analysed, firstly by applying statistical tests such as Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) (ADF) [3] and Kwiatkowski–Phillips–Schmidt–Shin (KPSS) [4]. In addition, autocorrelation (ACF) is applied to monitor the correlation of a feature across time. Furthermore, stationarity tests are carried to assess whether features are stationary or non-stationary.

In testing non-stationarity, a few parameters are considered such as: mean, variance, and autocorrelation. For example, p-value with a greater value than 0.5 is representing the non-stationary in ADF test. On the other hand to assess stationarity, the KPSS test is the opposite of ADF as a higher p-value indicates stationarity.

6.1.1 Prediction using Bayesian inference

If we want to compute the probability of having a certain contaminant by having different values for features in the predictive model, Bayes rule can be used to find the conditional and joint probabilities of the features. In other words, we are interested in finding out what is the probability of a contaminant being detected, (being in a state representing one of class values) whenever the state of other features changes.

This probability is based on the Bayes theorem, which aids to find two variables are independent of one another. For instance, $V1$ is independent of $V2$ if $P(V1|V2) = P(V1)$.

Future work for applying Bayesian’s predictive model could look at the underlying features within the network. For instance, hidden variable discovery can be used to capture unknown features along with the observed features.

6.1.2 Data classification

Data is converted to numerical values, scaled, and the class values are assigned to represent five categories of contaminants. Note that samples with missing data have been removed in the preprocessing stage.

6.2 Experimental set-up

For the implementation, R was utilised for all of experimental results which have been carried out.

Hierarchical clustering (agglomerative) and complete linkage are exploited to characterise different types of contaminants. They begin with each sample/data point in a distinct subgroup and successfully combines clusters based on the two features.

Figure 12: Elbow Method to find the optimal number of clusters for 100 samples.

Figure 13: Optimal number of clusters for 10000 samples.

6.3 Preprocessing and data preparation

Data is normalised and scaled in order to be analysed. The distances between observation values are calculated based on the Euclidean distance. All missing values were omitted from the dataset.

A tree-like diagram (dendrogram) is illustrated, where the x-axis shows the data points and y-axis indicates the distance of split or merge. The colour coding is used to determine which partition is assigned to which contaminant class types. BT, BG, PSL, and BareSubs (bare substrate) are colour coded by red, blue, green, and black, respectively.

6.4 Discussion

Finding the optimal number of clusters is determined by using the Elbow method and represented in Figures 12,13.

The hierarchical clustering by calculating the minimum distance between the clusters before merging (single linkage) performs effectively and obtained 79 out of 100 correctly allocations in the 4 different clusters (accuracy) as shown in the following table.

Clustering Linkage	Single	Complete	Average
Accuracy	79%	42%	74%

The visualisation of clustering method is demonstrated in the Figure 14, in which overlapped coloured data points represent the clustering performance and

Figure 14: Visualisation of clustering.

Figure 15: Single cluster and real class values.

as it is obvious is not significant comparing to the non-overlapped data points in the following Figure 15.

7 Experiment: Convolutional neural networks

7.1 Task description

In this section we will investigate the possibility of applying a fully convolutional neural network with residual links on classifying biological hazards. In this case we will concentrate on institution 8 data which used biological samples and IR absorption.

7.2 Experimental set-up

The data from institution 8 consists of a 526 files with a 1672 vector array of the absorption spectra. We noted that one file was dimensionally inconsistent with the spectra (i.e. it was longer than the rest of the data) and thus this data was removed from the rest of the experiments. This gave a total sample size of 525 sets of spectra. These were arranged into 70% training and a 30% test sets. The python package SciKits was utilised for the machine learning.

7.3 Methods

The residual neural network model was set up with the following configuration:

Input	Value
Block	64 filters
Block	128 filters
Block	128 filters
Convolution	3 filters, length 2
Batch Normalization	
ReLU	
GAP	
Softmax	

With a block layout of:

Input	Value
Sub-block	length 8
Sub-block	length 5 Convolution of size 1
Sub-block	length 3
Addition	ReLU

With a sub-block layout of:

Value
Convolution
Batch normalisation
ReLU

This was trained using Keras with a TensorFlow back end, with optimiser Adam(0.001), loss: categorical cross entropy and 1000 epochs.

7.4 Discussion

The accuracy on the training data was: 59%. The accuracy on the test data was: 66%. The confusion matrix for the test data is shown in the table 8.

	BG	BT	Non-hazardous
BG	66	0	6
BT	27	23	2
Non-hazardous	17	1	16

Table 8: Confusion matrix of BG, BT and Non-hazardous. It can be seen that non-hazardous is being predominantly misclassified as BG.

The higher accuracy in the test, compared to the training data suggests that the sample size is too small to effectively train and test this type of deep learning approach. The accuracy on unseen data may therefore be improved by training with a larger dataset. In addition the steady increase in the accuracy over the epochs could suggest that a larger number of epochs for training will also improve the accuracy. The risk associated with the increase is the potential to over-fit the classifier and which would result in a decrease in accuracy.

8 Experiment: Automated delineation of contaminant versus substrate on the 3D data

In institute 5 three BG and BT samples of three different concentrations were deposited onto four substrates, including wood, metal, glass and polycarbonate. They were then illuminated using two different sources (at wavelengths of 280 nm and 365 nm) and the resulting intensities recorded through a wavelength range of 400 nm to 700 nm.

The datasets contain a number of data cubes including; the raw data from the 280 nm and 365 nm, a pair of processed data cubes at 280 nm and 365 nm and finally a reflection data cube which consists of the ambient light observed off the sample without either light source enabled.

Since within these 3D datasets the sample and substrate spectra were mixed without annotation, for subsequent machine learning we need to develop an automated strategy for isolating sample spectra and labelling them appropriately.

8.1 Visualising and understanding the data cubes

First we visualised the data in spatial Cartesian (x,y) coordinates with the z axis containing results at different wavelengths. Here we will illustrate both the 280 nm and 365 nm results of the processed data for the glass sample.

As seen in Figure 16, the top two plots are from the processed datacube at 280 nm and the bottoms two are from 365 nm. The surface plots are of the sample at around 454 nm with the corresponding 1D intensities plots at y index location of 200. This was chosen as to give an illustration of the noise and detected signal strength. We can clearly see two significant deposits of the sample at 365 nm however at 280 nm we observe a large amount of noise at the sample locations.

We decided to apply a log-Anscombe transform ($\mathcal{A}\{..\}$) Eq. 1 to the dataset, which is a variance-stabilising transformation that transforms the Poisson distributed data to an approximate standard log-Gaussian distribution [2], this is shown in Figure 17. The transformation can clearly be seen as enhancing the image and revealing information that normally would have been hidden by the surrounding noise.

$$\mathcal{A}\{f(x)\} = \log \left(2\sqrt{f(x) + \frac{3}{8}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Looking at the raw datacubes we can identify the three sample regions, however, this data contains unwanted ambient excitation as shown in Figure 18.

Samples on different substrates can dramatically effect performance as a wood sample is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 16: Top row left to right, shows the spectral 2D spectral response at 280 nm with the corresponding, 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y-axis). Bottom row left to right, shows the corresponding 2D spectral response at 365 nm and 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y-axis)

8.2 Identifying sample borders

In order to analyse the dataset with machine learning, we have the challenge of identifying and labelling both the bacteria and background information. We begin with the following signal (Figure 20a) which depicts two peaks where we can clearly see the bacteria on the substrate.

Identifying the regions of BT/BG signal can formally be expressed as to isolate the regions of bacteria from the noise, in essence this can be accomplished by finding the tails of the the most dominate peaks in Figure 20a. The plan of attack is to take the second derivative of the signal to locate the regions where the signal transitions from a negative (on the y axis) to positive (indicating the leading edge of a pulse) and from a positive to a negative y axis value (indicating the trailing edge of a pulse). However, applying this technique to the data in this form will not allow us to easily identify the desired pulse edges.

We can mitigate this problem by removing the noise from the signal while retaining the bacterial information. Lets begin by defining our signal to be $U(x)$ and transforming it to the frequency domain by applying the following Fourier

Figure 17: Top row left to right, shows the Anscombe transform of the spectral 2D spectral response at 280 nm with the corresponding, 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y -axis). Bottom row left to right, shows the corresponding Anscombe transform of the 2D spectral response at 365 nm and 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y -axis)

transform operator $\mathcal{F}\{\dots\}$, as shown in Eq. 2.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{U}(\psi) &= \mathcal{F}\{U(x)\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} U(x)e^{ix\psi} dx\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

The resulting signal power $I(\psi)$ in the frequency domain is shown in Figure 20b. In what follows; we define I to be the signal power for any complex amplitude U , with U^* representing the corresponding complex conjugate. Therefore, Eq. 3 is the resulting signal power $I(\psi)$ of the complex amplitude $\tilde{U}(\psi)$, after the application of the Fourier transform.

$$\begin{aligned}I(\psi) &= \tilde{U}(\psi) \cdot \tilde{U}^*(\psi) \\ &= |\tilde{U}(\psi)|^2\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

Figure 18: Top row left to right, shows the raw data of the spectral 2D spectral response at 280 nm with the corresponding, 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y-axis). Bottom row left to right, shows the Raw data of the 2D spectral response at 365 nm and 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y-axis)

We can design a filter in a manner that will preserve the bacterial information while removing any unwanted noise, in this case we want to retain the bacterial information which is encoded in the signal located around centre (in Figure 20a, the value 44 along the x-axis; the x-axis can be converted to the respective unit but has been left as array index values to ease implementation). The majority of the information we are interested in is centred around the central peak and the adjacent sidebands.

If we create a filter with a bandwidth response of just over 20 units we can strip away the noise. In order to accomplish this we apply the following Gaussian filter (Eq. 4) to the spectral signal, Figure 20b. The action of Eq. 4 on the signal effectively filter out both the low and high noise frequency components and the gradual shift in the background. Both the central frequency ψ_c and the bandwidth of the filter ψ_0 were tuned by visual inspection.

$$g(\psi) = \frac{1}{\psi_0\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\psi-\psi_c}{\psi_0}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

Figure 19: Top row left to right, shows the spectral 2D spectral response at 280 nm with the corresponding, 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y-axis). Bottom row left to right, shows the 2D spectral response at 365 nm and 1D horizontal slice response at 100cm (y-axis)

For this instance we set the bandwidth to 6 and the centre to 44, giving the Gaussian filter shown in Figure 20c

Applying the Gaussian filter Eq. 4 in Figure 20c to the signal in Figure 20b will give us the resulting spectral as shown in Figure 20d. The action of which is described in Eq. 5.

$$\tilde{U}'(\psi) = \tilde{U}(\psi)g(\psi) \quad (5)$$

We now back-transform Eq. 5 to the spatial domain by performing an inverse Fourier transform operator $\mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\dots\}$, defined and performed in Eq. 6, giving us the filtered signal $U'(x)$. The power $I'(x)$ of the resulting complex amplitude $U'(x)$ is depicted in Figure 20e.

$$\begin{aligned} U'(x) &= \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\tilde{U}'(\psi)\} \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{U}'(\psi)e^{-ix\psi}d\psi \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Figure 20: Signal processing steps applied to the datacube. a) Intensity response from the 365 nm optical source. This is a horizontal slice across the sample illustrating the locations and intensity of the 3 sample locations. b) The signal in the spectral domain from a). c) Spectral profile of the applied Gaussian Filter. d) Signal after Gaussian filtered applied. e) Signal after Gaussian filtered applied. f) Spectral profile of the applied Gaussian Filter. g) Second derivative of the Intensity profile with the edges of the regions identified by the derivative crossing zero.

We can now clearly see the signal peaks generated by the concentration of the bacteria in Figure 20e. We also observe a third peak which is the bacterial sample with the lowest concentration which can only now be observed after we removed the spectral noise.

$$\frac{d^2 I'}{dx^2} = \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{U}(\psi) g(\psi) e^{-ix\psi} d\psi \right|^2 \quad (7)$$

Using the power signal $I'(x)$ from Figure 20e can now more easily determine the regions of bacterial signal from the background noise and thus determine both the leading and trailing edges of the peaks. We can automate and accurately determine the exact edges of the peaks by performing the second derivative (as shown in Eq. 7) on the data, give us the resulting Figure 20f. We can now clearly see the regions where the signal crosses the zero line at both the leading and trailing edges of the pulse. We can now use this information to accurately calculate and mark the regions where we have the bacteria.

8.3 Annotation

By analysing the filtered signal (Figure 20f) and applying the above procedure we can now accurately determine the boundaries of the sample and label them accordingly.

On applying the above procedure on the whole datacube which has been summed along the frequency axis (the filtered summed datacube is shown in 21a), we can create the resulting mask which identifies which part of the data are within the bacterial sample and the background noise, shown in Figure 21b. We can now use this masked information to train machine learning models to accurately identify bacteria on a noisy substrate.

8.4 Discussion

Data cubes provide a plethora of information about the intensity spectrum. By using the technique illustrated above to locate the sample within a flattened version of the sample slide, we can pinpoint the spectrum inside and outside the sample. While extracting the spectrum for every pixel as a 1D matrix, we can apply accurate labels to the data. These labelled spectra can then be given to supervised machine learning techniques for further insight.

(a) Full spectrum of the signal after filtering.

(b) Regions of signal and noise identified by the algorithm.

Figure 21: Data calcification mask. a) Datacube, after the Gaussian filtering procedure and sample region identification, Here we can clearly identify the regions where the sample is located on the substrate. b) Masked region of the dataset indicating the regions of samples and noise.

9 Conclusion and future work

We have demonstrated during the TDSG that machine learning techniques are suited to the classification and detection of hazardous chemical and biological agents on different substrate material. In the case of single point (1D) spectral measurements (more specifically institute 2 and 8) we demonstrated that dimensionality reduction and different logistic regression techniques can be applied successfully to this dataset. These results provide a baseline assessment of how this dataset performs when using a conventional machine learning approach. We envisage a continuation of this work would entail the application of more modern machine learning techniques that would include methods such as deep neural networks, and would involve appropriate hyperparameter tuning. In regards to our investigation of the training of convolutional neural networks using a labelled set of background and hazardous, and background and non-hazardous pairs of spectra, the network structure would be the same as that used in section 7, but would have the advantage of learning differences between the spectra, rather than trying to identify the signals of hazardous materials in isolation. This is proposed to improve transferability of the training from lab conditions to a wider range of substrate materials as could be found in the real world.

The main future work for this project is to improve information signal extraction from raw data and conversion (filtering and signal identification from background noise) as well as to explore more sophisticated machine learning techniques more suited to the dataset, but which were not considered due to the impracticality of implementing them fully in the short strict time frame allowed during the TDSG.

9.1 Classifiers for 1D Data

As summarised in the discussion in Section 5 with classifiers on reduced dimension subspaces, further avenues to investigate are:

- incorporating substrate material as a feature variable,
- trying higher dimensions for PCA,
- more extensive hyperparameter tuning, and
- addressing data imbalance in the training data.

9.2 Autoencoders

In future work we intend to use the labelled 3D data cube spectra and investigate the possibility to map them into a common latent space representation or embedding. To do this, we would explore the following techniques from signal compression and using deep learning with an encoder-decoder system, as described in this section. Due to the short nature of the Turing Data Study

Group (TDSG) and the restrictions imposed by the Turing Safe Heaven Environment, we were only able to consider the following potential machine learning (ML) techniques as our initial intention was to preform this ML operation within the allotted time frame. Below is a brief description of the machine learning techniques considered and how we would preform an initial investigation.

9.3 Encoder-decoder implementation details

During the Alan Turing Data Study Group, we created Python code for five different encoder-decoder systems with the intention of preforming the ML on institution 5 dataset. All systems assume a 80%/20% sample split into training and testing set respectively. The three substrate / sample combinations considered were represented in the classes as shown in Table 9.

	Class	Substrate	Deposit
0	Background	Bare substrate	No Deposit
1	GR and PR	Glass/Polycarbonate	BG deposit
2	GG and PG	Glass/Polycarbonate	BT deposit

Table 9: The three classes assumed for the dataset.

In Table 9, first letter described the surface, either “G” for glass or “P” for polycarbonate. The second letter denoted the bacterial species applied to the surface, either “R” for species “BG” or “G” for species “BT”. Other surfaces, “W” for wood and “M” for metal were not considered here. Due to the porous nature of wood the entire volume of the applied sample was no longer detectable on the surface. In the case of metal, the surface proved to be highly reflective which resulted in overloads. The applied controls, “BG control” and “BT controls” were not considered, during the Data Study Group time frame. However, this would not be the case in following on this research and all datasets and variables would be investigated.

During the TDSG only the textfiles for the “raw” data were used looking at wavelength 280nm and 365nm as well as background. This “raw” data had not been subjected to any form of correction which was found for some of the other input available. These files had been separated from a larger collection into a subfolder “input”. Each textfile contained a list of 78 values, hence 78 was the number of features. Importing the samples meant to convert the list of features to create a data frame with dimensions (n_samples x n_features). However, this in turn required to flatten the 2D dataframe into a 1D tensor. This has not been done yet due to lack of time. After conversion such a tensor can then be put in any of the autoencoders developed. For future work, the data will also need to be extracted from files containing labelled spectra as described in section 8.3.

The basic code for all autoencoders is based on simple commonly used applications. The particular sets of hyperparameters for each autoencoder will need to be found by further investigation and exploration. Training and assessment will need to be carried out and a model created. The aim for this application is

to create a feature vector from a 3D datacube to be used in supervised learning to identify the two species “BG” and “BT” on different surface media.

Filename
“simple_encoder_decoder.py”
“deep_encoder_decoder.py”
“1D_autoencoder.py”
“LSTM_autoencoder.py”
“TripletLoss.ipynb”

Table 10: List of python files that were created in order to explore the machine learning potential of institute 5 dataset.

9.4 Simple encoder-decoder

The simple encoder-decoder considered, only uses one dense layer to compress information and one dense layer to extract information from the compression. The encoder-decoder utilised the optimiser “Adam” [5], ReLU activation function [9] and the loss function “binary cross-entropy”.

Encoder	Dense(6, activation=“relu”)
Decoder	Dense(6, activation=“relu”)
Optimizer	Adam loss function: binary cross-entropy

Table 11: Configuration of simple encoder-decoder

9.5 Deep encoder-decoder

The deep encoder-decoder considered had the same basic architecture as the simple encoder-decoder but then expands with some “batch normalization” [6] and an additional dense layer when compressing and extracting. The final dense layer uses a sigmoid activation function rather than rectified linear units (ReLU). The characteristics of which are shown in Table 12.

9.6 1D autoencoder

An even more increased level of complexity is comprised in the 1D autoencoder, its configuration is shown in Table 13. Here the dense layers in the encoder are replaced by 1D convolutional layers followed by batch normalisation and MaxPooling. For the decoder, the batch normalisation has been replaced by an UpSampling1D layer. A final 1D convolutional layer uses a sigmoid rather than a ReLU activation function.

Encoder	Dense(6, activation="relu") Batch Normalisation Dense(encoding_dim, activation="relu")
Decoder	Dense(6, activation="relu") Batch Normalisation Dense(window_length, activation="sigmoid")
Optimizer	Adam loss function: binary cross-entropy

Table 12: Configuration of Deep encoder-decoder

Encoder	Conv1D(16, 3, activation="relu", padding="same") Batch Normalisation MaxPooling1D(2, padding="same") Conv1D(1, 3, activation="relu", padding="same") Batch Normalisation MaxPooling1D(2, padding="same")
Decoder	Conv1D(1, 3, activation="relu", padding="same") Batch Normalisation UpSampling1D(2) Conv1D(16, 2, activation="relu") Batch Normalisation UpSampling1D(2) Conv1D(1, 3, activation="sigmoid", padding="same")
Optimizer	Adam loss function: binary cross-entropy

Table 13: Configuration of 1D autoencoder

9.7 LSTM: (long short-term memory) autoencoder

Here we considered the LSTM encoder with the configuration in Table 14. The LSTM autoencoder components LSTM() and RepeatVector() are used with default settings as given in the Keras package.

9.8 Triplet Loss

Following the essentials of an encoder-decoder system, we wanted to enrich the latent space by including the labels of the dataset. Triplet Loss is a customised loss function for the encoder that incorporates the distances between data points in the latent space to encourage clustering of similar labels.

The idea is to measure the distance between the selected point, or anchor point, and two other data points, one within the anchor's own class and one outside. The loss function takes these distances to push the model to minimise the distance between points in the same class and maximise the distance between points in different classes.

Encoder	LSTM(encoding_dim)
Decoder	RepeatVector(window_length) LSTM(1, return_sequences=True)
Optimizer	Adam loss function: binary cross-entropy

Table 14: Configuration of LSTM autoencoder

For our dataset, we started re-implementing an example of Triplet Loss for the MNIST Numbers dataset for one dimensional, labelled spectra. If the embedding was enriched, we hoped to have similar vector maths capability to word2vec so samples could be abstracted from whatever surface they are seen on or the spectroscopic technique, as well as separated between each biological hazard. This would also be applicable to other similarly labelled datasets.

9.9 Additional future work

Other possibilities that could be explored and have not been considered here are:

- Anomaly detection
- Wavelet transformation
- Functional regression
- Factor analysis
- 2D convolutions

10 Team members

- **Ranjeet S. Bhamber** Ranjeet is a Senior Postdoc at the University of Bristol, as part of the BioSpi Laboratory. His background is in Theoretical Physics, numerical computing and Data Science and works on a range of topics from Photonics, wireless communications, Bioinformatics to Veterinary applications. He designed, developed, and implemented the automated delineation of irregular shapes on noisy substrates, the 3D visualisation of institution 5 datasets, and contributed to the writing of this report.
- **Robert Chin:** Robert is a PhD student in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, in a joint program between The University of Melbourne and University of Birmingham. His background is in control theory, optimisation, and machine learning. He worked on using PCA for dimensionality reduction, and building classifiers on the reduced dimension subspaces with IR biological and chemical data.

- **Andrew W. Dowsey** Andrew is Professor of Population Health Data Science at the University of Bristol, and group leader of the BioSpi Laboratory. He is a Turing Fellow and holds research programmes in data science methodology for mass spectrometry omics, antimicrobial resistance epidemiology, and animal biometrics. Prof Dowsey was the data science lead for this Data Study Group.
- **Kate Highnam:** Kate is a PhD student at Imperial College London, based in South Kensington. After working in industry as a machine learning engineer for cyber security applications within Capital One, she pursues a degree to further her career and understanding of research in her field. During this study group, Kate joined Melanie and Ranjeet to develop a labelled corpus from data cube samples and worked on the encoder-decoder latent space with triplet loss.
- **Phiippa McCabe:** Philippa is a PhD student with Liverpool John Moores University. She is working as part of the OActive H2020 project, using machine learning to model knee osteoarthritis. Her goal for the future is to continue working with machine learning approaches in the healthcare domain. During this data study group her contribution was the work and written section on classifiers on reduced dimension subspaces for IR of biological samples.
- **Laura Merritt:** Laura is a PhD student with the University of Reading, based at the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. She studies the fitting of dispersal kernels for use in predicting species range shifts under climate change. She contributed to this report by completing and writing the section on fully convolutional neural networks with residual links. She was also the facilitator for this data study group team.
- **Melanie Vollmar:** Melanie is a Postdoc working at Diamond Light Source, the UK's national synchrotron facility, a particle accelerator. She is funded by a BBSRC grant which is held by Diamond and CCP4, a computational group within Science and Technology Facilities Council (now UKRI) dedicated to macromolecular X-ray crystallography which is used to investigate the atomic structure of proteins. Within the MX village at Diamond, Melanie is responsible to investigate and develop machine learning applications to be deployed in automated data analysis pipelines to support users and help triage data from the ever increasing datarates produced by user experiments. Her contribution to the data study group was the exploration and suitability of autoencoders in this challenge.
- **Leila Yousefi** Post Doctoral Researcher at Brunel University London and University College London project funded by The Alan Turing Institute. She obtained a PhD degree in Artificial Intelligence in Medicine at Computer Science Department Brunel University London. The research area: Educational Data Mining, Time series Biomedical data analysis, Disease Prediction, Patient Clustering, Bayesian Modelling, Discovering Hidden/unmeasured variable cause-and-effect relationships between disease risk factors in a complex correlations metabolic network.

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